

**RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF THE POLLUTION STATE OF WATER
RESERVOIRS IN MODERN CONDITIONS**

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Annotation. The article analyzes the current state of pollution of open water bodies. According to the analysis of the literature and personal observations, the water of water bodies is mainly polluted with sulfates and iron. At the same time, water oxidation and turbidity are also considered to be the main water quality indicators.

Keywords: population, water resources, hygienic requirements, oxidation, sulfates, iron, ecology

**RESULTATY ANALYSIS ZAGRYAZNENIYA VODOEMOV V
SOVREMENNYX USLOVIYAX**

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Abstract. V state analiziruyutsya dannye o sostoyanii zagryazneniya otkrytykh vodeemov v nastoyashchee vremya. Na osvanonii dannyx literatury i izvetsila sobstvennyx issledovaniy ustanovlena chto voda vodoemov v osnovnom zagryaznyayutsya sulfatami i zheletom. A takje mutnost i okislaemost yavlyaetsya odin iz osnovnykh pokazateley kachestva vody vodoemov.

Keywords: population, water resources, hygiene requirements, oxidation, sulfates, iron, ecology.

RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF WATER BODIES POLLUTION IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Annotation. The article analyzes the data on the state of pollution of open water bodies at the present time. Based on the literature data and the results of our own research, it has been established that the water of reservoirs is mainly polluted with sulfates and iron. And also turbidity and oxidation is one of the main indicators of water quality in reservoirs.

Keywords: population, water resources, hygienic requirements, oxidizability, sulfates, iron, ecology.

Relevance. Nowadays, the rational use of water resources and their protection are also of great importance. Encouraging the protection of water resources also ensures the rational use of other natural objects and their ecological and legal protection. The ecological and legal protection of water resources and encouraging their rational use require the ecological and legal protection not only of water and water objects, but also of other natural resources. Special attention is paid to improving the environmental situation in the country, including the protection of water objects, the rational use of natural resources, as well as the prevention of emergencies in the event of floods and mudflows. Among natural resources, water is of particular importance, as it is a source of life.

Water, as a natural resource, has the property of biological purification by itself. It is purified under the influence of sunlight and the activity of organisms. That is, if 50% of bacteria are purified in 24 hours, 0.5% of pollutants remain in 96 hours, but it is difficult to purify heavily polluted water. The growth of irrigated land and the use of various pesticides, mineral fertilizers and plant protection products in

the cultivation of agricultural crops, as a result of which their residual amounts in wastewater exceed the permissible norms, have also led to the emergence of water problems, and at the same time, structural changes have occurred associated with the expansion of land areas intended for cotton cultivation[4,8]. In Uzbekistan, water resources of inland rivers account for 18% of the total need. About 82 percent of the total water demand is covered by the interstate resources of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya. The total flow of these rivers is 123.08 kilometers. Based on this indicator, in accordance with the intergovernmental agreement of the Aral Sea basin countries, water consumption limits and water distribution ratios have been established between the countries of the region. If in 2015 the total water deficit in Uzbekistan amounted to 3 billion cubic meters, then by 2030 it may reach 7 billion, and by 2050 it may reach 11-13 billion cubic meters. Analyses show that the water in the Aral Sea basin is gradually decreasing [5,6,9]. In particular, if water shortages were repeated every 6-8 years until 2000, then the survival of humanity, the existence of the entire planet, depends on water. It is no secret that in today's global climate, the demand for water is increasing and due to inefficient use, water shortages are occurring in some regions. This is especially noticeable in the agricultural sector, which is the largest consumer of water. In particular, the cotton industry is considered the most water-intensive agricultural crop and requires frequent irrigation, which is why the water problem in Central Asia remains a significant environmental problem. Uzbekistan has created strong legislation to address the problem, in particular, there is the Law "On Water and Water Use". Article 11 of the Law: Conditions for the placement, design, construction, reconstruction, repair, restoration and commissioning of enterprises, structures and other objects that affect the state of waters and water bodies, stipulates the following: When placing, designing, building, reconstruction, repair, restoration and commissioning of enterprises, structures and other objects that affect the state of waters and water bodies, When introducing new technological processes, it is necessary to ensure

rational use of water, taking into account the requirements of protecting the health of the population and primarily satisfying their needs for drinking water and household needs, as well as a convenient regime for the discharge of collector-drainage waters and wastewater [1,2,3,7]. This includes measures to ensure accounting for water withdrawn from and returned to water bodies, protection of waters from contamination, pollution and depletion, prevention of the harmful effects of waters, minimization of land flooding, protection of lands from salinization, waterlogging or drought, as well as preservation of favorable natural conditions and landscapes.

The results obtained. Based on the above, we examined the state of pollution of water bodies and analyzed the water of open water bodies for organoleptic, chemical and general sanitary indicators. The results of laboratory analysis established the following: In 2018, the total number of samples taken was 104, which were tested for dry residue, total hardness, chlorides, sulfates, iron, nitrates, color, turbidity, hydrogen index and oxidation.

Table 1

Results of analysis of samples taken from open water bodies in 2018

No.	Indicators	Samples obtained	Samples that did not meet hygienic requirements (%)
1	dry residue	16	13.3
2	chlorides	3	2.8
3	sulfates	16	13.3
4	iron material	50	48.0

When analyzing the results of laboratory testing, the following was found: 16 samples (13.3%) of the samples taken for dry matter, 38 (36.5%) for total hardness,

3 (2.8%) for chlorides, 16 (13.3%) for sulfates, 50 (48.0%) for iron, and 82 samples for turbidity did not meet hygienic requirements.

Table 2

Results of analysis of samples taken from open water bodies in 2019

No.	Indicators	Samples obtained	Samples that did not meet hygienic requirements (%)
1	dry residue	2	1.1
2	Chlorides	7	3.6
3	Sulfates	2	1.1
4	iron material	5	2.8

The total number of samples taken in 2019 was 173, of which 2 (1.1%) samples for dry matter, 2 (1.1%) samples for sulfates, 5 (2.8%) samples for iron, and 12 samples for oxidation did not meet hygienic requirements.

Conclusion: From the results obtained, it can be concluded that according to the results of sanitary chemical analysis of water in water bodies, some samples did not meet hygienic requirements, especially in terms of turbidity, total hardness and the amount of sulfates. This serves as the basis for developing preventive measures for the sanitary protection of water resources from pollution.

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